

The Effect of Work Load, Discipline and Employee Income of Employees on Aparature Performance Civil Country through Work Satisfaction as an Intervening Variable on Medan Education Department

Riki Priyandi¹, Paham Ginting², Yeni Absah³

¹ Postgraduate Students, Department of Management, Faculty of Economics and Business at University of Sumatera Utara, Indonesia

^{2,3} Postgraduate Lecturer, Department of Management, Faculty of Economics and Business at University of Sumatera Utara, Indonesia

Corresponding Author: Riki Priyandi

ABSTRACT

The Education Office is an element of implementing government affairs in the field of education. The Education Office as led by the Head of Service who is domiciled and is responsible to the Mayor through the Regional Secretary. The Department of Education as having the task of assisting the Mayor in carrying out government affairs in the field of education is the authority of the Region and the task of assistance given to the City Government. Along with its development there is a decrease in employee performance in the Department of Education due to the incompatibility of providing additional income with workload and employee work discipline. The purpose of this study was to determine and analyze the effect of workload and work discipline on performance through additional income as an intervening variable. This type of research is associative quantitative. The population of the study was 108 employees and the sampling technique used was simple random sampling with 85 respondents. Data analysis uses path analysis. The results showed that the variable workload and work discipline significantly influence performance through additional income.

Keywords: *Workload, Discipline, Additional Competence, Performance*

INTRODUCTION

The success of an organization or company is strongly influenced by

employee performance. Every organization or company will always try to improve employee performance, with the hope that what the company's goals will be achieved. According to Mangkunegara (2013: 67) performance is the result of quality and quantity of work achieved by an employee in carrying out their duties in accordance with the responsibilities given to him. In achieving employee performance, human resource factors are very dominant in influencing employee performance. In addition, good performance professionalism is how an employee is able to show work behavior that leads to the achievement of company goals and objectives, for example by managing human resources to lead to good work results.

The scope of human resource management in general discusses matters relating to humanity including employee job satisfaction. Job satisfaction is a general attitude of an individual towards his job, a person with a high level of job satisfaction shows a positive attitude towards the job, a person who is dissatisfied with his job shows a negative attitude towards the job (Robbins, 2011: 139). Satisfaction felt by employees at work is an indication that employees have happy feelings in carrying out work duties. Nurul hidayah, (2016) in his research stated that job satisfaction has a

positive and significant effect on performance. While other studies from Sari, and Susilo, (2018) provide different results that job satisfaction is not a variable that is able to mediate the relationship between compensation for performance.

The welfare benefits provided by an organization are to increase the morale of its employees, so that they feel safe, comfortable and calm at work that will increase their productivity. Additional income obtained by the state civil service or incentives must be in accordance with regulations that have been issued by the government. Providing additional employee income is very useful to improve performance. Meriana Madjid, (2016) in her research concluded that income benefits had a positive and significant effect on performance. However, Sicillia emma sumampouw, (2017) argues that the most dominant factor influencing performance is not work benefits but motivation.

Each company requires its employees to apply several criteria in achieving optimal performance including the completion of workload. According to Dhania (2010), workload is a number of activities that require expertise and must be completed within a certain period in physical and psychological form. Workload provided by the company becomes its own assessment. The leader will see the extent to which employees are able to complete the tasks given and this will affect the additional income of employees and have an impact on performance. Saefullah (2017) in his research stated that there is a negative influence between workload on work productivity. However, lukiyana, firman and paradise (2017) suggested the results that workload had a positive and significant effect on performance appraisal.

Discipline is something that becomes a benchmark to find out whether the role of a leader as a whole can be implemented well or not. Discipline is also a form of employee self-control and regular implementation in showing the level of sincerity of the work of employees in a

company or organization, where employees who do not comply with the rules set by the company will get sanctions. Therefore this disciplinary action cannot be applied haphazardly, so it requires wise consideration. Tri, Wijayati and Wardoyo, (2016) concluded that work discipline had a positive and significant effect on work productivity. Another study conducted by Fitriasari, (2016) stated that work discipline had a positive effect not significantly on performance.

Medan City Education Office is the agency responsible for carrying out development in the field of education that refers to increasing human resources with the main task of carrying out regional authority in the field of education. The function of the Office of Education is to formulate technical policies in the field of education and as implementing technical operational policies in the field of education. The policy of providing additional employee income conducted by the education office in the hope of increasing the morale of the entire apparatus in the Medan City Government.

In essence there are still employees who are less eager to work even though they have received additional employee income. This is because the benefits provided are evenly distributed to each employee but the work results achieved by the employees are different. Employees who have work performance in the medium and low categories get the same additional employee income as employees who have high performance categories. This raises the lack of employee morale to provide more work.

Medan Mayor Regulation No 44 of 2017 regarding additional employee income which has several criteria including work discipline, workload and performance appraisal. Regarding the work discipline of the state civil apparatus has received a special assessment that is coming on time, returning home on time, attendance at work and never getting a punishment for being undisciplined. Regarding work performance is an assessment in terms of quality and

quantity of employees. For workloads, employees get special assignments such as the PA, KPA, Treasurer, and other civil servants of the country which are equaled with a Mayor Decree. In understanding the characteristics of employee behavior need to be considered and understood the factors that influence the level of enthusiasm in working.

Medan City Education Office really needs employees who have excellent quantity and quality, because the tasks and obligations that need to be accounted for are not an easy matter, therefore high employee work performance is required in carrying out their duties, required to be creative, innovative and able to be effective in carrying out tasks. But in reality the employees are not as perfect as expected by the institution in running the wheels of the organization. The performance results of employees in the Medan City Education Office need to be reviewed. Declining performance has an impact on organizational sustainability, in this case the organization is demanded to be able to provide maximum results such as work completion, discipline and problem solving skills.

On the other hand the results of interviews of several staff in the sub-section of staffing and general relating to a decrease in employee work discipline as seen from absenteeism levels in October 2018 - March 2019 were unsatisfactory, it can be seen from the percentage of absenteeism. With frequent employees absent from their jobs, it means that they are still not optimal in carrying out their duties and responsibilities. This also certainly affects the systems and programs that have been planned by the Medan City Government Education Office.

In this regard, there are several violations that result in the absence of employees that often occur at the Medan City Education Office, including the presence of employees who sometimes leave early and arrive late. This illustrates that the firmness and supervision of the leader is still not good, and this can disrupt

the process of work activities and systems that have been planned in advance. This indicates the lack of employee discipline.

There are employees who have heavier workloads but the results of the assessment given are the same as those with workloads of the medium category. So that the assessment of work performance produced is very incompatible with the work that has been charged by the state civil apparatus in the Medan City Education Office. Some employees sometimes doubt the results of the assessment. Even though the assessment is officially done by the leadership of the Medan City Education Office, employees expect the results of the assessment to be in accordance with working conditions.

Hypothesis

Based on the concept presented by the author, the research hypothesis can be formulated as follows:

1. Workload has a negative and significant effect on job satisfaction at the Medan City Education Office.
2. Work discipline has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction at the Medan City Education Office.
3. Additional employee income has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction at the Medan City Education Office.
4. Workload has a negative and significant effect on performance at the Medan City Education Office.
5. Work discipline has a positive and significant effect on performance at the Medan City Education Office.
6. Additional employee income has a positive and significant effect on performance at the Medan City Education Office.
7. Job satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on performance at the Medan City Education Office.
8. Workload has a negative and significant effect on performance through job satisfaction at the Medan City Education Office.

9. Work discipline has a positive and significant effect on performance through job satisfaction at the Medan City Education Office.
10. Additional employee income has a positive and significant effect on performance through job satisfaction at the Medan City Education Office.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

This study uses quantitative is associative, namely research that is more based on data that can be calculated to produce an assessment (Sugiyono, 2014). Associative research is research to examine the relationship / influence of independent variables on the dependent variable.

The population in this study were all state civil servants in the Medan City Education Agency, with 108 employees. Sampling in this study with probability sampling techniques. According to Sugiyono (2010: 63), Probability sampling is a sampling technique that provides equal opportunities for each element (member) of the population to be elected as a sample member. The random sampling technique in its calculation technique uses the Slovin formula. The reason for the use of the Slovin technique is because the most representative method of calculation provides equal opportunities to each member of the population. So that the number of samples in this study were 85 respondents.

Data collection techniques in this study were carried out by making a list of questions where this technique gives responsibility to respondents to read and answer questions and researchers can provide an explanation of the purpose of the survey and questions that are not understood by respondents and responses to the questionnaire can be directly collected by researchers after filled in by the respondent. And responses to the questionnaire can be directly collected by researchers after being filled in by respondents using a Likert scale which contains 5 levels of answer preferences as choices. The documentation

study was carried out by collecting and studying supporting data in the form of a brief history of the Medan City Education Office, organizational structure, and several other data obtained directly from the Medan City Education Office and an Interview, the process of obtaining information for research purposes by means of question and answer. This interview was addressed directly to Medan City Education Department employees.

Types and sources of data used in this study are the types of primary data and secondary data. Primary Data is research data obtained directly from the original source (not through an intermediary source) and the data is collected specifically to answer research questions in accordance with the wishes of researchers Indriatoro and Supomo (2012: 129). Secondary Data according to Supomo (2012: 129), states that secondary data is data that is a source of research data obtained indirectly through intermediaries (obtained and recorded by other parties). Secondary data are generally in the form of evidence, notes, or historical reports that have been compiled in archives (documentary data) which are published and not published.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Workload Has a Negative and Significant Effect on Job Satisfaction

Based on the results of data analysis it is known that the value of $t_{count} > t_{table}$ of workload (X1) is $-2,962 > 1,99$ and a significant value of $0,004 < \alpha 0,05$, workload has a negative and significant effect on job satisfaction. This indicates that if the workload is increased it will reduce the job satisfaction of employees in the Medan City Education Agency. The workload in the Medan City Education Office is in the form of job duties, additional work provided by the leadership.

Job satisfaction is one's happy feeling about the job itself which is in accordance with the educational background so that it is able to do and complete the work and tasks it faces to the maximum.

Conversely, if employees who do not get job satisfaction will feel bored with the demands given by superiors, so that work will be hampered and the method of completion will not be maximized.

There are two important elements in job satisfaction, namely job values and basic needs (Lockedalam Waluyo, 2013: 125). One of the important problems in this organization is how the organization can create a situation so that employees can get individual job satisfaction properly and how they want to work based on desires that are not affected by workload.

Workload is a work situation that must be held accountable for its completion by employees with a heavy enough workload with limited capabilities possessed by employees. If employees work below the standard, the workload is overloaded. Workload will be felt by individuals who lack capability in the field of work being occupied or the number of jobs that cannot be completed on time.

This is in line with research conducted by lukiyana, firman and paradise (2017) which states that workload has a negative and significant effect on job satisfaction. Workload is considered capable of reducing employee job satisfaction because of the need to be completed.

Work Discipline Has a Positive and Significant Impact on Job Satisfaction

Based on the results of data analysis, it is known that the value of $t_{count} > t_{table}$ of work discipline (X2) is $3.353 > 1.99$ and a significant value of $0.001 < \alpha 0.05$, so that work discipline has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction. This indicates that work discipline has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction.

Discipline is defined as an orderly situation where people who are members of an organization are subject to the rules that have been happily determined by a person / group of people. Work discipline includes timeliness, utilization of facilities, work responsibilities, and adherence to agency regulations. In fact, some employees are on

time when they enter the office, leave their desks before the allotted time, and employees are still delaying work.

Utilization of facilities that have not been well targeted such as hotspots / wifi, internet networks, these facilities are provided to employees to facilitate the work provided and to input data. There are still many employees who misuse internet network facilities for personal interests such as playing online games and personal social media. The company has a role in managing employees to comply with all rules, norms set by the company so that employees work in a disciplined and effective manner.

Discipline is one's awareness and willingness to obey all applicable organizational rules and social norms. Various rules / norms set by a company have a very important role in creating discipline so that employees can obey and implement these regulations. The rules / norms are usually followed by sanctions given if there is a violation. These sanctions can be in the form of verbal or written reprimands, suspension of positions and even dismissal depending on the amount of violations committed by employees.

It was intended that employees work with discipline and be responsible for their work. If employees have high work discipline, they are expected to be able to complete tasks quickly and precisely so that job satisfaction arises. The results of this study are in line with research conducted by Saputra and Turnip, (2018) that work discipline has a positive and significant effect on employee job satisfaction.

Additional Employee Income Has a Positive and Significant Impact on Job Satisfaction

Based on the results of data analysis it is known that the value of $t_{count} > t_{table}$ of additional employee income (X3) is $4.253 > 1.99$ and a significant value of $0.000 < \alpha 0.05$, so that additional employee income has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction. This indicates that if

employee income is increased it will increase employee job satisfaction.

Broadly speaking, additional employee income itself is divided into two namely material and non material. Additional employee income has a broader meaning than wages or salaries. Wages or salaries place more emphasis on financial rewards, while additional income includes financial and non-financial services. Additional employee income is one of the ways that can be provided by the company so that it can increase job satisfaction and impact on employee productivity towards the company.

Provision of additional incentives outside salary for each employee in the Medan City Education Office has been routinely carried out. Additional income is proven to have a positive effect on employee job satisfaction; the results of this study are consistent with the opinions of the results of previous studies conducted by Hidayah, (2016) and Muhamad R, et al (2014) that compensation has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction.

Workload Has a Negative and Significant Effect on Employee Performance

Based on the results of data analysis it is known that the value of $t_{count} > t_{table}$ of workload (X1) is $-2.057 > 1.99$ and a significant value of $0.043 < \alpha 0.05$, so that the workload variable (X1) has a negative and significant effect on performance. This indicates that if the workload is increased it will reduce the performance of Medan City Education Department employees. Increasing the target that must be achieved by a company then, also increases the workload on employees, if the workload continues to increase without an appropriate division of workload, employee performance will decline. Workload is one element that must be considered for a worker to get harmony and high work productivity.

Workload is the main parameter that must be considered by the company in an effort to improve employee performance. A

set or number of activities that must be completed by an organizational unit or position holder within a certain period. Appropriate workload will provide high performance output. Education Office employee workloads greatly affect employee performance; employee workload must be balanced in order to be maximized in productivity performance. The workload of employees in the Office of Education includes additional work, overtime and duties from the leadership.

Workload is proven to have a negative effect on performance. The results of this study are in accordance with Fahmi (2016) research that high work stress decreases performance. Work stress is influenced by workload that is so heavy. The higher the workload will cause the performance of employees is not optimal / decreased. Performance will be maximized if workload indicators are met in a balanced manner such as targets to be achieved, work conditions and work standards. The work tag determined by the company must be in accordance with the ability of employees and their capacity. Conditions of work which include the views held by individuals regarding the conditions of work that exist in the Department of Education.

Work Discipline Has A Positive And Significant Impact On Employee Performance

Based on the results of data analysis it is known that the value of $t_{count} > t_{table}$ of work discipline (X2) is $2.312 > 1.99$ and a significant value of $0.023 < \alpha 0.05$, so that work discipline has a positive and significant effect on performance This indicates that if discipline work is increased, it will improve the performance of Medan City Education Department employees.

One of the factors that influence employee performance is work discipline. According to Simamora (2018: 125) discipline is a procedure that corrects or punishes subordinates for violating rules or procedures. Work discipline is a tool used by leaders to communicate with employees

so that they are willing to change a behavior and as an effort to increase awareness and willingness to obey all company rules and social norms that apply.

When the level of work discipline of a company is high, it is expected that employees will work better, so company productivity increases. In addition, good work discipline will improve work efficiency as much as possible, do not spend a lot of time for the company to just improve the discipline and time can be used to achieve company goals.

The effect of work discipline on employee performance was stated in Ariana's (2013) study. In his research mentioned that the company could pay more attention to the ability of employees, retaliation against employees, sanctions against violations of discipline, tighter supervision in an effort to improve or improve employee performance. These things prove that work discipline is an important factor in improving employee performance.

With good work discipline from employees such as arriving on time, carrying out work in accordance with what has been set by the company, obeying company regulations will be able to improve the performance of these employees so that the company's targets will be achieved. This research is relevant to research conducted by Elqadri, et al (2015) which states that work discipline has a positive and significant effect on employee productivity.

Additional Employee Earnings Have a Positive and Significant Impact on Employee Performance

Based on the results of data analysis, it is known that the value of $t_{\text{arithmetic}} > t_{\text{table}}$ of additional employee income (X3) is $3.357 > 1.99$ and a significant value of $0.001 < \alpha 0.05$, so that the additional variable employee income has a positive and significant effect on performance. This indicates that if additional employee income is increased it will improve the performance

of Medan City Education Department employees.

This shows that in determining the additional amount of income employees do not consider the educational background and experience of employees while working in the Education Office. When the Office of Education is wiser in determining the amount of additional income, the employee will improve the quality of its performance will have an impact on performance and psychological which will also have an impact on employee commitment in the Medan City Education Office.

Providing wise additional income such as salary is one form of the Office of Education's policy that makes employees active at work. Giving additional benefits must also prioritize the Office of Education policy indications that are based on education, experience and responsibility given to the employee in determining the amount of additional income so that employees feel given appropriate compensation and will compete in contributing to the Education Office. This is in line with research conducted by Ignatius, Dianti and Khosari, (2017) that compensation has a positive and significant effect on performance.

Job Satisfaction Has a Positive and Significant Impact on Employee Performance

Based on the results of data analysis, it is known that the value of $t_{\text{count}} > t_{\text{table}}$ of job satisfaction (Z) is $4.906 > 1.99$ and a significant value of $0.000 < \alpha 0.05$, so that the job satisfaction variable has a positive and significant effect on performance. This indicates that if job satisfaction is increased it will improve the performance of Medan City Education Department employees

Satisfaction can be formulated as a general response of workers in the form of behavior displayed by employees as a result of perceptions about matters relating to their work. A worker who enters and joins an organization has a set of desires, needs,

desires and past experiences that come together and form a hope that is expected to be fulfilled in the place of work.

Job satisfaction will be obtained if there is a match between the expectations of workers and the reality obtained at work. Workers' perceptions about matters relating to their work and job satisfaction involve a sense of security, a sense of fairness, a sense of enjoyment, a sense of passion, status and pride. This perception also involves the work situation of the worker concerned which includes work interactions, working conditions, recognition, relations with superiors, and promotion opportunities. Employees will feel comfortable in carrying out their obligations.

This is in line with research conducted by Sari, Heru and Susilo, (2018) which states that job satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on performance. If job satisfaction increases, employee performance will also increase. Job satisfaction at work makes something that is able to connect between tasks and responsibilities this is able to provide optimal performance in employees.

Workload Has a Negative and Significant Effect on Employee Performance Through Job Satisfaction

Based on the results of data analysis, it is known that workload has a negative and significant effect on performance through job satisfaction. Although job satisfaction has a negative effect on performance, the relationship of workload to satisfaction and direction performance is negative. This indicates that if the workload is increased it will reduce job satisfaction and have an impact on the performance of Medan City Education Department employees. Conditions where an increase in workload will be followed by a decrease in performance as seen from the revision of work.

Workload provided by superiors is routine and always increases the number of hours worked which makes employees often leave longer than actual time. In addition,

the workload provided must also be completed on time such as work reports and several other jobs such as attending schools, both public and private.

High workload has a negative impact on job satisfaction. This is certainly due to the absence of a good match of income, duties and work demands between divisions which are considered not the same but the income provided by the Education Office is the same. This is in line with research conducted by Wijaya, (2018) as well as research from lukiyana, firman and paradise (2017) that workload has a negative and significant effect on employee performance.

Work Discipline Has a Positive and Significant Impact on Employee Performance Through Job Satisfaction

Based on the results of data analysis, it is known that work discipline has a positive and significant effect on performance through job satisfaction. This means that the higher the employee's work discipline, the higher job satisfaction will be. Discipline is a tool used by leaders of the Office of Education to communicate with employees so that they are willing to change a behavior and as an effort to increase awareness and willingness to obey all company regulations and applicable social norms.

The existence of work discipline is able to shape employee satisfaction with their work. Employees not only formally work at the office, but are also able to feel and enjoy their work, so they will not feel bored and are more diligent in their activities. The employees will be more happy in working if the work can be done easily, it is because the employees work according to the existing work procedures and procedures.

Medan City Education Office always strives to improve the level of employee discipline including being honest in carrying out tasks, being responsible for their respective jobs, working according to the time determined by the company, being on

time, following work procedures and being able to use work equipment appropriately .

If employees work according to applicable regulations, it will have a positive effect on employee performance. This reason is reinforced by the theory of Hasibuan (2014) who argues that discipline is the awareness and willingness of a person to obey all company regulations and applicable social norms. This is in line with research conducted by Karollah, Syarifah and Nathasya (2018) that high work discipline can improve performance by making sure that employees remain aware and willing to obey and obey the rules in the company.

Additional Employee Income Has a Positive and Significant Impact on Employee Performance Through Job Satisfaction

The results showed that additional employee income had a positive and significant effect on performance through job satisfaction. Additional employee income is very important for employees to meet their daily needs with family. However, it is not only important for additional employees that employee income is also important for the company to get qualified employees and reduce employee turnover which will increase company costs. Additional employee income provided by the Department of Education to employees can affect many things such as work decisions, productivity, performance and others. The greater the additional employee income received, job satisfaction, productivity, and performance will also be better. This can be seen from the actions taken such as discipline, work morale, work morale.

Therefore every company must pay attention to additional employee income. given so that employees have a good job decision so as to produce things that provide profits for the company. Although basically job satisfaction is something that is individual, each individual has a different level of job satisfaction. This is in line with

research conducted by Hidayah, (2016) and Ignatius et al (2017) that compensation has a positive and significant effect on performance through satisfaction.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

CONCLUSIONS

The conclusions in this study are:

1. Workload has a negative and significant effect on job satisfaction at the Medan City Education Office.
2. Work discipline has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction at the Medan City Education Office.
3. Additional employee income has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction at the Medan City Education Office.
4. Workload has a negative and significant effect on performance at the Medan City Education Office.
5. Work discipline has a positive and significant effect on performance at the Medan City Education Office.
6. Additional employee income has a positive and significant effect on performance at the Medan City Education Office.
7. Job satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on performance at the Medan City Education Office.
8. Workload has a negative and significant effect on performance through job satisfaction at the Medan City Education Office.
9. Work discipline has a positive and significant effect on performance through job satisfaction at the Medan City Education Office.
10. Additional employee income has a positive and significant effect on performance through job satisfaction at the Medan City Education Office.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The suggestions in this study are:

1. It is better for the Medan City Education Office to pay more attention to the level of workload provided by monitoring

each subordinate's work so that employees with high, moderate and low workloads are known to minimize employee social jealousy, especially for employees who have long worked in the Education Office.

2. It is better if employee work discipline is improved again by giving new regulations such as tougher sanctions from the Office of Education to employees in terms of bonus cuts, incentives and overtime pay if employees cannot attend on time and do not comply with applicable regulations.
3. It is better for the addition of more effective employee income to be given to employees by looking at the results of work provided by employees in each division. Provision of additional income should not be generalized to employees who have class levels and position positions but rather to the results of monthly and annual work reports from employees.
4. Increased employee job satisfaction should be improved by providing employee work system development with more attention to employees. Know what is the basis of the desires and needs of each employee. So that everything that becomes the duty and responsibility of employees can be carried out with enthusiasm and a sense of responsibility.
5. It is better for employees to improve their performance by achieving work performance that has been set by the company. Improving performance can be with a discussion between superiors and subordinates about what are the barriers to employees in working and the desires of employees in following activities and work that has never been done at the office so that employees will feel more empowered it is also supported by employee satisfaction in undergoing work which is carried out while working at the Department of Education is to provide appropriate compensation for services provided by employees.

6. This research can also be used as a reference for further research relating to concepts or theories that support the knowledge of human resource management and which are the limitations of this study.

REFERENCE

1. A.A. Anwar Prabu Mangkunegara. 2010. *Evaluasi Kinerja Sumber Daya Manusia*, Refika Aditama, Bandung.
2. AA. Anwar Prabu Mangkunegara, 2013, *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia Perusahaan*, Remaja Rosdakarya, Bandung.
3. Ahmad Badawi Saluy, Risamawati (2018), The Influence of Transformational Leadership Style, Work Discipline and Compensation on Teacher Performance SMK Global Mulia Bekasi, *Journal of Economics, Business and Management (SJEEM) Juni, 2018; 5(6): 465-474*.
4. Ahmad Saputra , Relly Rotua Turnip, (2018), Pengaruh motivasi, komunikasi dan disiplin terhadap kepuasan kerja PT PLN (Persero) P3B Sumbagut, *Jurnal Manajemen Bisnis STIE IBBI, Volume 29 No.2*.
5. Alex S. Nitisemito, 2014, *Manajemen Personalia*, Ghalia Indonesia, Jakarta.
6. Andrew E. Sikula. 2011 *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia*. Erlangga. Bandung
7. Banta Karollah Syarifah Nathasya (2018), Pengaruh Tunjangan Prestasi Kerja dan Disiplin Kerja terhadap Kinerja ASN Negeri Sipil pada Badan Kepegawaian Aceh, *SIMEN (Akuntansi dan Manajemen) STIES Vol. 9 Issue 1 (2018) hal.13-22*.
8. Dessler, Gary. 2015. *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia*. Jakarta: Salemba Empat.
9. Dewi Tri Wijayati Wardoyo (2016), The Influence of the Discipline and Compensation against Work Productivity (Study on the Security Services Company, PT Garuda Milky Artha Surabaya), *International Journal of Business and Management; Vol. 11, No. 1 : 2016*.
10. Encep saefullah , listiawati, asti nur amalia (2017), Pengaruh beban kerja dan stres kerja terhadap produktivitas kerja karyawan , *Akademika, Vol. 15. No.2 Agustus 2017*.
11. Hasibuan, Malayu S.P. 2010. *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia*. Jakarta: PT Bumi Aksara.

12. Handoko, T. Hani. 2011. *Manajemen Personalia dan Sumberdaya Manusia*. Yogyakarta: Penerbit BPFE.
13. Ghozali, Imam. 2018. *Aplikasi Analisis Multivariate dengan Program IBM SPSS 25*. Badan Penerbit Universitas Diponegoro: Semarang.
14. George Kafui Agbozo, The Effect of Work Environment on Job Satisfaction: Evidence from the Banking Sector in Ghana, *Journal of Human Resource Management 2017 :5(1): 12-18*.
15. Jacqueline Fritzie Najooan, (2018) Pengaruh tunjangan kinerja terhadap kinerja ASN pada dinas pertanian kabupaten minahasa, *Agri-SosioEkonomi Unsrat, Volume 14 Nomor 1, Januari 2018 : 11 – 24*.
16. Jimmy Ignatius, Ine Luna Dianti , Sujati Khosari, (2017), Pengaruh kepuasan kerja dan kompensasi terhadap kinerja karyawan (studi kasus di PT. Dharma Busana Elok Singgasana), *jurnal eksekutif volume 14 no. 2*.
17. Lukiyana, firman davi firdaus (2017), Pengaruh beban kerja dan lingkungan kerja terhadap prestasi kerja karyawan dengan kepuasan kerja sebagai variabel intervening di bagian gudang pada PT. Sarijasa Transutama Jakarta, *Majalah Ilmiah Institut STIAMI, Volume 14, No. 02, September 2017*.
18. Meriana Madjid (2016), Pengaruh tambahan penghasilan pegawai (TPP) dan kemampuan kerja terhadap kinerja ASN pada badan perencanaan, penelitian dan pembangunan daerah (bappeda) kabupaten morowali, *Jurnal Katalogis, Volume 4 Nomor 8, Agustus 2016 hlm 85-9*.
19. Muhammad Idris (2018), The Impact of Education and Training, Work Discipline and Organizational Culture on Employee's Performance: The Study of Disaster Management and Fire Department in Palembang City, Indonesia, *International Journal of Human Resource Studies ISSN 2162-3058*.
20. Muhamad Rizal (2014), Effect of Compensation on Motivation, Organizational Commitment and Employee Performance (Studies at Local Revenue Management in Kendari, *International Journal of Business and Management Invention*.
21. Maniar Fitriarsari (2016), analysis the influence of compensation work, discipline work, and workplace physical of the performance of employees with work performance as variable interveningnya (study in PT. Mandiri Karya Perdana), *Journal of Management Vol.02 No.02 , Maret 2016*.
22. Nurul hidayah, (2016), Pengaruh kompensasi terhadap kinerja karyawan dengan kepuasan kerja sebagai variabel intervening (studi kasus pada karyawan bagian keuangan dan akuntansi UNY), *Jurnal Profita Edisi 4 Tahun 2016*.
23. O'Donnell dan Eggemeier. (2011), *Workload Assessment Methodology*. New York: Wiley.
24. Oxy Rindiantika Sari, Heru Susilo, (2018), Pengaruh kepuasan kerja terhadap kinerja karyawan dengan organizational citizenship behavior sebagai variabel intervening (studi pada karyawan PTPN X - Unit Usaha Pabrik Gula Modjopanggoong Tulungagung), *Jurnal Administrasi Bisnis (JAB)/Vol. 64 No. 1*.
25. Panagiotis Trivellas (2017) The effect of job related stress on employees' satisfaction: A survey in Health Care , *rocedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences 73 (2013) 718 – 726*.
26. Rivai, Veithzal. (2013). *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia Untuk Perusahaan Dari Teori ke Praktik*. Jakarta: Raja Grafindo Persada.
27. Soleman, Aminah. 2011. Analisis Beban Kerja Ditinjau Dari Faktor Usia Dengan Pendekatan Recommended Weiht Limit. *Jurnal Arika, Vol.05 No.02*.
28. Sutrisno, Edi. 2010. *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia* Edisi pertama. Jakarta: Kencana Prenada Media Group
29. Sutoyo (2016), Pengaruh beban kerja, lingkungan kerja dan motivasi terhadap kinerja ASN pada Dinas Bina Marga Propinsi Sulawesi Tengah, *Jurnal Katalogis, Volume 4 Nomor 3, Maret 2016 hlm 187-195*.
30. Suwanto. 2011. *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia dalam Organisasi Publik dan Bisnis*. Alfabeta. Bandung.
31. Syaifuddin fahmi (2016), Pengaruh stres kerja dan konflik kerja terhadap kinerja ASN karyawan pada PT. Omega Mas Pasuruan, *Jurnal Ekonomi Modernisasi, 12,3 (2016), 107-116*.
32. Tohardi, Ahmad. 2011. *Pemahaman Praktis Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia*, CV. Mandar Maju, Bandung.

33. Wibowo. (2010). "*Budaya Organisasi*". PT. Rajagrafindo Persada, Jakarta.
34. Wijaya, A (2018), Pengaruh beban kerja terhadap kepuasan kerja dengan stres kerja sebagai variabel mediasi pada pekerja di Hotel Maxone di Kota Malang, *Parsimonia vol. 4 no. 3*.
35. Yuddin, (2017), Influence of the Compensation, motivation And Discipline work Against The work Achievement Teacher At Sma Negeri Jeneponto Regency west Bangkala I, *Journal of Research in Business and Management Volume 5 ~ Issue 2 (2017) pp: 83-88*.
36. Zaenal Mustafa Elqadri, Dewi Tri Wijayati , The Influence of Motivation and Discipline Work against Employee Work Productivity Tona'an Markets, *Review of European Studies; Vol. 7, No. 12; 2015*.

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